

ON THE STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOR AND FIRE RESISTANCE OF CARBON FIBERS AND STEEL REINFORCED HIGH-STRENGTH AXIALLY LOADED CONCRETE COLUMNS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new method aimed at overcoming the steel cage congestion for high-strength concrete (HSC) columns. The proposed method uses carbon fiber mesh as internal confinement reinforcement together with the conventional transverse steel reinforcement providing the required confinement level as well as fire resistance for the columns. A special test setup that includes a portable furnace was developed to perform tests of HSC columns exposed simultaneously to high temperatures and axial loads. The test results show the effectiveness of the dual confinement system compared to that of the conventional steel-reinforced columns in terms of strength and ductility.

KEYWORDS

Fire resistance, Confinement in columns, Carbon fiber textile, High-strength concrete

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, numerous studies have focused on investigating high strength concrete (HSC) behavior (ACI-441, 2018; Antonius et al., 2017; Aslani & Bastami, 2011; Kunze, 1995; Lee et al., 2018; Luther & Bauer, 1987; Schmidt & Hoffman, 1975; Shah et al., 1983; Zia et al., 1991). HSC columns are commonly utilized in high-rise building construction with an aim to reduce their size and thus to increase the available space, especially at the bottom parking floors. To enhance the ductility and load-bearing capacity of concrete columns, transverse steel reinforcement is typically employed to confine them. However, as the strength of the concrete increases, a larger volume of confinement reinforcement is required (ACI-441, 1996). This increased use of reinforcing steel in HSC applications results in steel congestion, which hinders the smooth flow of concrete (Eid et al., 2018). Several studies have explored the use of FRP (Fiber Reinforced Polymer) sheets as a solution to address this issue by enhancing the confinement effect in concrete columns and reducing the lateral steel reinforcement amount (Eid et al., 2009, 2019; Lim & Ozbakkaloglu, 2014; Ortlepp et al., 2009; Ortlepp & Ortlepp, 2017; Ozbakkaloglu, 2013b, 2013a). Additionally, Eid and Paultre (Eid & Paultre, 2017) proposed a model to assess the impact of the combined steel lateral reinforcement and FRP confinement system on high strength concrete columns. However, it is worth noting that externally wrapped FRP has low fire resistance, necessitating the addition of insulation for minimal fire resistance (Chowdhury et al., 2012).

This study focuses on investigating a novel solution involving a hybrid system that combines steel hoops and carbon fibers for confinement. This system is implemented internally within the high strength concrete column, providing the confinement benefits and fire resistance. Earlier studies (Eid et al., 2019; Shachar et al., 2022a, 2023, 2022b) have demonstrated the feasibility of this method, and the current research further examines and verifies the method's effectiveness through tests.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

This work is dealing with the effectiveness of hybrid, steel-hoops with carbon fiber lateral mesh, as a concrete column confinement system. Experiments were performed on high-strength concrete circular specimens with a diameter of 250 mm under ambient and elevated temperatures. The results of the first stage of this work, of specimens that were tested under ambient conditions, were presented also in Shachar et al. 2023. This paper includes initial results of the second stage, where specimens were tested under elevated temperatures. The paper also presents a comparison of the second stage's results with those of the first stage. In order to evaluate the dual-system confinement effectiveness and plan the experiments, the Eid and Paultre (Eid & Paultre, 2017) model was used to calculate the stress-strain relationship of circular high-strength concrete columns. Although this model originally referred to columns with internal steel hoops and externally wrapped FRP sheets, it was adapted for the current work (with internal FRP). The proposed system includes an internal polymer-free fiber mesh replacing the external FRP sheet in the original model.

Tested Specimens

The circular specimens are of 250 mm diameter and 950 mm height. All specimens were longitudinally reinforced with six 12-mm deformed steel bars with a yield strength of 500 MPa and with lateral 10-mm deformed steel hoops, spaced at either 80 or 130 mm with a strength of 500 MPa. Table 1 shows the tested specimen's details, where the parameter ρ_h in the table represents the conventional transverse reinforcement ratio while the equivalent carbon fibers thickness is denoted t_{eq} . The parameter t_{eq} takes into account also the spacing of the fiber mesh and it is calculated by dividing the mesh unit area weight (only in the lateral direction) by the carbon fibers density. The carbon fibers mesh is polymer-free, uncoated without any resin, considering the need for their fire safety performance (two carbon mesh types were used: 'Q95' and 'Q71' produced by Solidian with a reported modulus of elasticity = 230 GPa and rupture strain = 0.013 mm/mm).

A load cell with a capacity of 5 MN was used to measure the axial load and the deformation in the vertical direction was measured by two LVDT's at each side of the specimen (see Figures 1 and 2). In addition, for the unheated specimens, longitudinal and lateral strains were also measured by strain gauges. The temperatures of the heated specimens were recorded by "K" thermocouples (TC) placed in seven locations over one line inside the mid-height cross-section (see Figure 1b).

Table 1: Details of three 950 mm length and 250 mm diameter circular columns.

Specimen	f_c [MPa]	Transverse steel	ρ_h [%]	Carbon fiber mesh	Carbon t_{eq} (mm)	Temperature (°C)
S80C0T0*	84.7	Ø10@80	1.78	None	0	ambient
S130C1T0	84.7	Ø10@130	1.10	1 layer Q95	0.095	ambient
S130C4T0	84.7	Ø10@130	1.10	4 layers Q71	0.285	ambient
S80C0T300	79.9	Ø10@80	1.78	None	0	300
S80C0T700	79.9	Ø10@80	1.78	None	0	700

*Control specimen

Figure 1: Experimental specimens details

The concrete mixtures included 2kg/m^3 Polypropylene fibers which were added to prevent spalling at elevated temperatures for high-strength concrete (BS-EN-1992-1-2, 2004). Two batches were used to cast the specimens (at a concrete plant). The mixture had a 0.3 water/cement ratio. The average compressive strengths were 99.6 and 94.0 MPa (at 28 days, 150-mm cubes) with standard deviations of 3.7 MPa and 6.0, respectively. The mean cylinder strengths is evaluated as 84.7 MPa and 79.9 (see Table 1) for the two batches (applying a conversion factor of 0.85 from cube to cylinder, EN 1992-1-1, 2004). The experiments were performed in the laboratory of the National Building Research Institute at the Technion - Israel Institute of Technology.

Experiments setup

The specimens were loaded in a rigid hydraulic 5-MN pressing machine with a manual stroke control. Two steel collars were used to restrain the column's edges and avoid stress concentration. The free unrestrained cover part of the column was of 810mm long. With a thin leveling layer of sand, the rougher side of the specimens was enveloped in a steel capping. The testing setups are shown in Figure 2a. The setup of the two columns tested under elevated temperatures is shown in Figure 2b. The column specimens were heated using a special tube furnace up to 300 °C and 700 °C (see next section) prior to the load application (see Figure 3).

Figure 2: Experimental setups

Figure 3: Tubic furnace for experiments under elevated temperatures and load

Thermal process

The heat application for specimens S80C0T300 and S80C0T700 is shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively. It is important to mention that the axial load application in the experiments occurred only after the temperature across the cross-section of the column had reached the desired target temperature with a tolerance of $\pm 50^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 4: Time-Temperature curves for several points in the cross-section of specimen S80C0T300

Figure 5: Time-Temperature curves for several points in the cross-section of specimen S80C0T700

Test results

The behavior of the specimens axially loaded under ambient temperature was characterized by first spalling of the concrete cover followed (at larger axial strains) by crushing of the concrete confined by the hybrid reinforcing system. The failure of the specimens was around the mid-height of the columns, as presented in Figure 6 and involved also a local buckling of the longitudinal reinforcement as shown in Figure 7a (as also reported by Shachar et al., 2023). The ambient-temperature, steel-confined specimen (S80C0T0) exhibited also a rupture of the lateral hoops, as shown in Figure 7a, and the hybrid confined specimens exhibited also full or partial rupture of the carbon strands, as shown in Figure 7b. Figure 6 also shows specimens S80C0T300 and S80C0T700 after testing. The specimens developed thermal elongation during the heating process and failed only due to the loading process. The failure mode of these pre-heated specimens is characterized by cover failure and longitudinal bars buckling.

The tests were stopped when the longitudinal steel buckled and the column's axial strains were very large. It can also be seen in Figure 7 that the concrete failure splits the aggregates as is known for high-strength concrete failure.

Figure 6: Specimens photos after the tests

Figure 7: Typical failure of specimens (Shachar et al., 2023).

The vertical measured displacements of the unheated specimens show good agreement between those of the strain gauges and those of the LVDT's. After the maximum load and at the failure of the concrete cover, the strain gauges went off scale due to the large level of strains, and the LVDT's measured continuously during the whole test.

Figure 8 shows the axial load-strain curves of specimens S80C0T0, S130C1T0, and S130C4T0. Figure 9 presents the axial load-strain (measured by the LVDT's) curves of the specimens S80C0T300 and S80C0T700 (under elevated temperatures). For the unheated specimens, Figure 8 shows that the most pronounced effectiveness of the confinement is in the unheated control specimen (S80C0T0) in terms of axial bearing capacity and ductility.

Figure 8: Load-Strain curves of the specimens at ambient temperatures (Shachar et al., 2023)

Figure 9: Load-Strain curves of the specimens at elevated temperatures

All specimens reached their peak load when the concrete cover failed. As compared with the control specimen S80C0T0, the peak load was somewhat lower in S130C1T0 and S130C4T0. There is a possibility that during high axial loads, the concrete cover may separate from the concrete core, which prevents the specimen from reaching its maximum load (determined by the model). In the literature (Cusson & Paultre, 1994; Foster et al., 1998; Paultre et al., 1996), it is reported that dense confinement system in high-strength concrete columns can cause longitudinal weakness planes between the core and the cover of the concrete. This phenomenon can also occur when carbon mesh is wrapped around steel cages like specimens S130C1T0 and S130C4T0.

Figure 9 shows, as expected, that the maximum axial load of the heated specimens is lower than that of the ambient temperature control specimen (3000 kN for S80C0T300, 2210 kN for S80C0T700, compared to 4500 kN reached by specimen S80C0T0). Moreover, for specimen S18C0T300, the failure of the concrete cover at the maximum load occurred at a lower axial strain than that of specimen S18C0T700. In addition, the ductility of specimen S18C0T700 was higher than the control S80C0T0 specimen, as well as specimen S80C0T300.

Carbon fibres mesh influence on the stress-strain relationship

The stress-strain behavior of the confined specimens are determined based on the technique presented by Shachar et al. (2023). The evaluated experimental stress-strain curves for S130C1T0, and S130C4T0 are plotted in Figure 10 with the Eid and Paultre model (Eid & Paultre, 2017) curves. The Figure shows a good agreement between the model and the experimental results of the unheated hybrid confined specimens. The figure shows that the confinement effectiveness is increased by increasing the amount of carbon fiber mesh. Moreover, the ductility of the hybrid specimens was lower than the conventional steel-reinforced specimen. However, it is worth noting that for the hybrid confined specimens the higher the mesh amount the higher the ductility reached by the specimen (Shachar et al., 2023).

Figure 10: Stress-strain curve for the hybrid confined specimens compared to their pre-evaluation of Eid and Paultre model (Eid & Paultre, 2017).

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a new method using carbon fiber mesh as internal confinement reinforcement together with conventional steel hoops providing the required confinement level as well as fire resistance for high-strength concrete columns. A special test setup that includes a portable furnace was developed to perform tests of high-strength concrete columns exposed simultaneously to high temperatures and axial loads.

Initial experimental results of five specimens are presented: three specimens were tested at ambient temperature and two specimens were simultaneously exposed to high temperatures and axial compressive loading. It is shown that the most pronounced confinement effectiveness was achieved by the unheated steel confined specimen in terms of axial bearing capacity and ductility. The results also show that the confinement effectiveness is increased by increasing the amount of carbon fiber mesh and that the maximum axial load of the heated specimens is lower than that of the specimen tested under ambient temperature. The failure of the concrete cover of the specimen heated to 700 °C occurred at a higher axial strain compared to the specimen heated to 300 °C. Moreover, it is demonstrated that the higher the temperature the higher the ductility reached by the axially loaded specimen.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.